

Article

Meiofaunal Abundance, Vertical Distribution, and Secondary Production from an Upwelling Coastal Area in Southern Peru (~14°16' S)

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Abstract

Meiofaunal assemblages are crucial components of benthic ecosystems, significantly contributing to organic matter cycling and energy transfer. However, baseline quantitative data from some upwelling systems remain limited. This study characterizes the abundance, vertical distribution, and secondary production of meiofauna at a coastal upwelling station off southern Peru (14°16' S) for July 2006 (Neutral conditions) and May 2007 (moderate La Niña, LN), using four-replicated sediment cores sectioned into 0–1, 1–2, 2–5, and 5–10 cm layers. While Nematoda (families Desmodoridae, Chromadoridae, Monhysteridae, Oxystominidae, Comesomatidae) dominated the community (>79% in all layers, both years), the total taxonomic richness did not differ substantially between study periods nor across the sediment column for 2006 or for 2007. Total density (0–10 cm) fluctuated between 3916 ± 2202 Ind 10 cm^{-2} in 2006 and 4203 ± 2274 Ind 10 cm^{-2} in 2007, with non-significant changes. Biomass ($\mu\text{gC } 10 \text{ cm}^{-2}$) in 2006 ranged from 80 ± 24 in the 5–10 cm section to 455 ± 134 in the 2–5 cm section. The uppermost 0–1 cm layer showed 238 ± 155 , while the 1–2 cm section reached 302 ± 69 . In 2007, biomass was consistently higher in the surface layers, with maximum values in the 1–2 cm section (500 ± 534), followed by the 0–1 cm section (376 ± 34). Hierarchical clustering produced depth-ordered groups with high within-depth similarity (>80–90%). SIMPER results identified *Desmodora*, *Comesomatidae*, and *Chromadoridae* among the top contributors to within-depth similarity and to the dissimilarity observed between surface and subsurface assemblages. A depth-related gradient of community composition was detected, suggesting vertical habitat heterogeneity modulated by several environmental factors; however, PERMANOVA analysis residuals (96.73%) indicate a high variation not explained by ENSO phase, sediment section, or their interaction, suggesting other unmeasured factors explaining meiofaunal community structure. Meiofauna's production ranged from $2.836 \pm 0.049 \text{ gC m}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$ in 2006 to $3.106 \pm 1.566 \text{ gC m}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$ in 2007. These findings expand the limited knowledge on meiofaunal abundance and metabolic demands in this ocean region, fostering future efforts for comparative analyses across latitudes, depth gradients, and oceanographic regimes.

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1. Introduction

Most studies on benthic organisms along the Peruvian coast have focused on key ecological responses of megafauna (organisms clearly recognizable to the naked eye)

and macrofauna (i.e., invertebrates retained in a 500 μm sieve), groups defined by size criteria [1–3], their habitat types, and distribution patterns [4,5], including long-term analyses of recurrent, large-scale oceanographic events such as the warm phase (El Niño, EN) of the El Niño–Southern Oscillation (ENSO) [6,7], and uncertain future scenarios for benthos. Research along the continental shelf and slope further highlights the consistent presence of taxonomic groups such as Annelida, Mollusca, and Crustacea across benthic habitats, from shallow waters to deeper sites [8–10].

However, there is growing interest in analyzing the highly abundant yet poorly understood smaller sediment-dwellers [11–13]. Meiofauna, for instance, exemplifies a group comprising numerous phyla, including permanent (e.g., Kinorhyncha, Gastrotricha) and temporary members (e.g., polychaete juvenile forms, mollusk larvae), a distinction widely studied with respect to the developmental stage and adult size attained by each taxon [14]. This diversity is also evident in the organically rich, reduced sediments of the Peruvian shelf, a region with significant potential to harbor highly specialized and diverse meiofauna [15–17]. These communities exhibit high densities [15,18] and high biomass, particularly among ubiquitous free-living nematodes [19]. This presents a valuable opportunity to explore adaptability and ecological responses within a complex, large marine ecosystem.

Extreme oxygen deficiency ($<0.5 \text{ mL}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ or $22.5 \mu\text{M}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$) drastically restructures benthic communities and disrupts key functional processes such as reproduction, recruitment, and respiration [20,21]. At the phylum level, studies indicate rich protozoan and metazoan meiofaunal communities persist in surface sediments of Peru's central shelf and slope despite high hydrogen sulfide (H_2S) concentrations and near-anoxia [7,15,18]. Species-level analyses further reveal meiofauna thriving under chronic hypoxia/anoxia across shallow to deep habitats in central Peru, including dense populations of benthic foraminifers and free-living nematodes inhabiting both flocculent surface layers and deeper sediment strata [15,22].

Despite their ecological relevance, taxonomic studies of benthic systems, particularly those targeting small meiofauna-sized organisms, remain scarce along much of the Peruvian coast. This knowledge gap impedes a comprehensive understanding of benthic adaptations and ecological responses to local and remote stressors, including the influence of low-oxygen mid-water layers ($<0.5 \text{ mL}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$). These layers form a shallow, intense oxygen minimum zone (OMZ; upper limit $\sim 50 \text{ m}$) that modulates ecological processes locally and regionally [23].

Southern Peruvian regions ($\sim 13.5\text{--}15^\circ \text{ S}$) support rich benthic biota, including coastal seaweed formations, exploited megafauna (e.g., echinoderms, bivalves), diverse coastal pelagic fishes, and many other demersal and benthic species [10,24,25]. Macrofauna and megafauna studies along depth gradients reveal high standing biomasses of benthic organisms on the intertidal, shelf, and slope, suggesting distinctive energy flow and transfer mechanisms [26–28].

Some reports indicate that protozoan meiofauna thrive in shallow surface sediments within southern Peru's upwelling-dominated sector, representing a numerically dominant benthic component [29,30]. Despite their ecological significance for ecosystem dynamics and functionality, comprehensive baseline studies of this community remain scarce. To address this knowledge gap, this study characterizes meiofaunal composition, vertical distribution patterns, and estimates secondary production, a key metabolic property, in a representative southern Peruvian coastal area.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study Area

This study was conducted in Independencia bay ($\sim 14^{\circ}16' S$; Figure 1), a key coastal upwelling site within the Peruvian marine ecosystem [26,31]. The bay experiences persistent wind-driven upwelling that efficiently supports the fertilization of surface waters over this sector of the Peruvian shelf [31]. Contemporary analyses of coastal wind forcing reveal a persistent local maximum near Pisco ($14.8^{\circ} S$), where strong wind events (defined by alongshore velocities $\geq 10 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$) occur with notable regularity, typically lasting 2–3 days and recurring every 6–7 days during peak upwelling seasons. These events correspond to estimated wind stress values on the order of $\sim 0.16 \text{ N}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ [32], nearly double the climatological mean reported in recent studies in the Pisco-Marcona area ($\sim 0.08 \text{ N}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$), and are sustained by robust alongshore pressure gradients [33], sustaining upwelling-favorable conditions [34–36].

Year-round exposure to OMZ waters creates permanently reduced conditions in both the water column and sediments. These conditions drive H_2S release, generating extreme physiological stress unfavorable to invertebrates and fish [37]. While hypoxia and anoxia event frequency in Independencia bay remains poorly quantified, the area likely follows large-scale patterns observed in similar Peruvian shelf regions [21,38]. These patterns are closely linked to subsurface ventilation processes and high surface water productivity.

Figure 1. Study area and location (red triangle) of the sampling station (red circle) in Southern Peru (Independencia bay, $14^{\circ}16' S$).

2.2. Meiofauna Sampling and Processing

Sediment sampling occurred in July 2006 and May 2007 aboard the R/V José Olaya Balandra (Instituto del Mar del Perú, IMARPE) during a geological campaign, providing four undisturbed cores for biological analysis. Cores were visually inspected onboard, and only those exhibiting an intact sediment-water interface, clear vertical color stratification, and continuous lamination were selected. The overlying water was required to remain

clear, indicating minimal disturbance during retrieval, and any cores showing cracks, deformation, or surface mixing were excluded. At 32 m depth (14°16'31" S, 76°09'52" W), we collected two replicate cores per campaign using a monocoherer (Ø 8.4/9.0 cm; height: 63 cm) and two more with a mini-multicoherer (Ø 9.5/10.0 cm; height: 70 cm). Undisturbed selected tubes were subsampled onboard with a 3.6 cm internal diameter corer, sectioned into 0–1, 1–2, 2–5, and 5–10 cm intervals, and stored in labeled plastic jars. A relaxant solution (6% MgCl₂; 72.5 g L⁻¹) was added to minimize body distortion. Samples were preserved in 4% borax-buffered formaldehyde prepared in filtered seawater.

Laboratory processing included a brief (40 s) low-energy ultrasonic treatment (40 kHz, ≈100 W) using a laboratory ultrasonic bath to disaggregate sediment particles and facilitate meiofauna extraction. The treatment consisted of a single short pulse (40 s) applied prior to sieving, with samples immersed in filtered seawater at laboratory temperature. Ultrasound amplitude was kept at the bath's default (low) setting to avoid vigorous agitation; this conservative regimen and bath modality were specifically chosen to minimize mechanical damage to soft-bodied taxa (e.g., kinorhynchs, gastrotrichs) while maximizing detachment of organisms from sediment particles. This procedure has been previously tested and demonstrated to be suitable for fine and muddy sediments such as those off Peru, allowing the successful recovery of delicate taxa, including microturbellarians, small-sized nematodes [16,17], and larval forms [39] under variable oceanographic conditions [7]. Samples were washed sequentially through 500 µm (retaining macrofauna) and 46 µm (retaining meiofauna) sieves. The meiofauna fraction was stained with 0.5 g L⁻¹ Rose Bengal for initial identification and quantification under a stereomicroscope. Density (individuals, Ind. 10 cm⁻²) and biomass (µgC 10 cm⁻²) were calculated for depth-integrated (0–10 cm) and each section. Digital data and specimens were archived at IMARPE's Oceanographic Data Center and Marine Benthos Laboratory, respectively.

This study emphasizes the taxonomic analysis of highly abundant nematodes at the lowest taxonomic level. Other meiofaunal groups were identified at the phylum or class level. Foraminifera were excluded from the analysis because the sampling procedure used was not specific to this group, which requires the identification of a living fraction using high concentrations of Bengal Rose. Identification used phylum-specific pictorial keys [14,40–42] and general references for rare taxa [43–45]. Due to their high densities, ciliates were included in community analyses as numerically significant components. To evaluate the community diversity pattern along the sediment column, both Simpson's dominance index (λ) and Shannon's diversity index (H') were taken into account. However, as Simpson's index is highly sensitive to the presence of numerically dominant taxa, the complementary form ($1 - \lambda$) was used (which increases as dominance decreases and community evenness rises) to evaluate consistency in the diversity pattern. Shannon's index (H' , expressed on a log₂ scale) incorporates both species richness and evenness, with higher values indicating greater diversity in terms of both the number of taxa and their relative distribution. Concordant variation in both indices provides consistent evidence of changes in evenness and dominance, whereas divergence between them may reveal shifts in the richness of rare taxa (H') without substantial changes in dominance (λ).

The Chao2 estimator was employed to assess sampling completeness and estimate true taxonomic richness in this replicated survey design. This incidence-based metric is particularly appropriate for meiofaunal communities, where spatially aggregated distributions and cryptic taxa often result in incomplete detection despite adequate sampling effort. By quantifying the number of undetected taxa based on the frequency of rare species across replicates, this estimator provides critical insights into survey adequacy and, in addition, a more robust comparison of diversity patterns across environmental gradients and temporal conditions.

2.3. Biomass Estimations

Biomass estimation involved randomly selecting 50 nematodes per sediment section based on density ranges, while all available individuals from less abundant non-nematode groups were measured. Body dimensions of preserved specimens were quantified using a calibrated ocular micrometer at 100× and 400× magnification, converting measurements to volume and mass (wet/dry). Biomass calculations employed Andrásy's formula (1956) [46]:

$$V = C \times L \times W^2 \quad (1)$$

where V denotes volume in nanoliters (nL), C represents taxon-specific constants sourced from Feller and Warwick (1988) [47], L is body length (mm), and W is maximum body width (mm). For taxa lacking published constants, values from morphologically similar organisms were applied. Volumes were converted to wet weight (μg) using a specific gravity of 1.13 g cm^{-3} , with carbon biomass subsequently derived through standard conversion (dry:wet weight ratio = 0.25; carbon content = 40% of dry weight), and final values expressed as $\mu\text{gC } 10 \text{ cm}^{-2}$.

2.4. Production and Respiration Estimates

All taxa were incorporated into production and respiration estimates rather than focusing solely on dominant groups such as free-living nematodes. Meiofaunal production (P) was calculated using Tumbiolo and Downing's (1994) [48] empirical model for marine invertebrates:

$$\text{Log } P = 0.18 + 0.97 \text{ Log } B - 0.22 \text{ Log } W_m + 0.04 T_h - 0.014 T_h \text{ Log } (Z + 1) \quad (2)$$

where P represents production ($\text{g dry weight m}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$), B is biomass (mg dry weight), W_m denotes maximum body mass (mg dry weight ; adults only), T_h is bottom water temperature (16.5° C , July 2006; 16.0° C , May 2007), and Z is depth (m). Total meiofaunal respiration (R) followed Schwinghamer et al. (1986) [1]. Final P and B values were converted to carbon units ($\text{gC m}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$ and mgC m^{-2} , respectively).

2.5. Statistical Analysis

Meiofaunal density and biomass vertical distributions are presented as means \pm SD. Considering the sample size ($n = 4$ per period) and potential non-normality, a non-parametric Mann–Whitney U test was performed to assess significant temporal changes in meiofaunal community metrics between 2006 and 2007.

The analysis incorporated two ENSO periods, Neutral (2006) and moderate La Niña (moderate LN, 2007), considering variation across sediment depth strata. Univariate diversity indices (Shannon-Wiener H' [\log_2], Simpson's $1 - \lambda$) were computed per replicate/period to assess section-related trends. For multivariate analysis, fourth-root transformed data generated Bray–Curtis similarity matrices for hierarchical clustering (group-average linkage). SIMPER analyses identified the taxa contributing most to dissimilarities between ENSO phases and sediment depths. Two-way crossed ANOSIM determined significant dissimilarities (global R), while PERMANOVA tested fixed effects (period, section). Community gradients were further explored using canonical correspondence analysis (CCA). All analyses were conducted in R [49]. All statistics are reported with a significance threshold of $p < 0.05$, or less (e.g., $p < 0.01$) when indicated.

3. Results

3.1. Diversity

The taxonomic richness of the meiofaunal assemblage was dominated by the phylum Nematoda (e.g., families Desmodoridae, Chromadoridae, Monhysteridae, Oxystominidae, Comesomatidae). Although most specimens were not identified to lower taxonomic levels, it is important to note the recurrent presence of Copepoda and benthic Ciliophora in the surface sediment across both sampling campaigns, as well as occasional records of rotifers, gastrotrichs, nemertean, bivalves, and polychaete larvae.

Overall, total taxonomic richness did not differ substantially between study periods and varied only modestly with depth in the sediment column. In July 2006, the upper sections (0–1 cm and 1–2 cm) tended to exhibit the highest richness values (25.0 ± 2.10 and 22.0 ± 1.91 taxa, respectively). The deeper strata (2–5 cm and 5–10 cm) showed comparatively lower richness (19.0 ± 2.40 and 18.0 ± 2.40 taxa, respectively). In terms of relative frequency, nematodes dominated the assemblage, followed by copepods, ciliates, bivalves, and polychaetes. The proportional contribution of nematodes ranged from $79.5 \pm 19.4\%$ in the 1–2 cm layer to $91.8 \pm 7.5\%$ in the 5–10 cm layer (Table 1, Figure 2).

Table 1. Taxa richness ($S \pm SD$), meiofaunal densities ($\text{Ind } 10 \text{ cm}^{-2} \pm SD$), biomass ($\mu\text{gC } 10 \text{ cm}^{-2} \pm SD$), and respective relative density of free-living nematodes ($\% N \pm SD$) by section (cm), during July 2006 and May 2007.

	Section (cm)	S	Density	% N	Biomass	% N
2006	0–1	25 ± 2.1	1506 ± 719	91.7 ± 5.1	331 ± 155	57.5 ± 1.0
	1–2	22 ± 1.9	935 ± 946	79.5 ± 19.4	255 ± 69	97.3 ± 3.9
	2–5	19 ± 2.4	1121 ± 1148	90.5 ± 7.8	365 ± 134	98.2 ± 2.1
	5–10	18 ± 2.4	354 ± 353	91.8 ± 7.5	107 ± 24	95.2 ± 2.1
2007	0–1	25 ± 0.96	1278 ± 743	86.4 ± 11.5	368 ± 34	94.7 ± 15.2
	1–2	21 ± 0.96	1793 ± 1204	96.7 ± 1.8	346 ± 534	71.1 ± 6.9
	2–5	17 ± 2.36	780 ± 587	90.5 ± 7.3	196 ± 197	79.6 ± 45.0
	5–10	15 ± 2.38	352 ± 268	88.8 ± 6.4	82 ± 95	79.8 ± 8.0

For May 2007, taxon richness was again highest in the surface layer (25.0 ± 0.96 taxa at 0–1 cm; 21.0 ± 0.96 taxa at 1–2 cm), while the deeper sediment layers displayed lower values (17.0 ± 2.36 at 2–5 cm; 15.0 ± 2.36 at 5–10 cm). Nematoda remained the most abundant group, followed by Ciliophora, Copepoda, and Polychaeta, with nematode relative abundance varying between $86.4 \pm 11.5\%$ (0–1 cm) and $96.7 \pm 1.8\%$ (1–2 cm).

Statistical tests confirmed that there were no significant differences in total taxonomic richness between 2006 and 2007 for any sediment section (Mann–Whitney $U = 10.5$, $p = 0.561$). Similarly, within-year patterns of richness across the sediment column were not statistically significant for 2006 ($p = 0.678$) or for 2007 ($p = 0.900$). Concerning the diversity indexes, both indices show the same basic vertical and temporal pattern: the shallowest horizon (0–1 cm, red) consistently displays the highest diversity values (highest $1 - \lambda$ and highest H'), intermediate horizons (1–2 cm, green; 2–5 cm, turquoise) occupy intermediate positions, and the deepest horizon (5–10 cm, purple) has the lowest diversity, particularly in 2007. In addition, the Chao2 estimates suggest that between 2% and 28% of the true community richness remained undetected during the sampling effort, with the magnitude of underestimation varying substantially among depth sections and years.

Figure 2. Vertical distribution of the (A) density (Ind 10 cm⁻²), (B) biomass (µgC 10 cm⁻²), and relative density (%) of the total meiofaunal taxa (C) and most abundant free-living nematode taxa (D) (Other: *Spirinia*, *Anoplostoma*, *Leptonemella*, *Odontophora*, *Pselionema*, *Selachinematidae*) by sections of the sediment (cm) during July 2006 and May 2007.

Numerical magnitudes in the plots were indicative; in 2006, the surface layer (0–1 cm) had very high evenness/diversity ($1 - \lambda \approx 0.95-0.97$; $H' \approx 4.4-4.6$), whereas the deepest layer yielded $1 - \lambda$ values closer to $\sim 0.93-0.94$. In 2007, the deepest layer (5–10 cm) undergoes a marked decline ($1 - \lambda$ drops to $\approx 0.91-0.92$ and H' to $\approx 3.6-3.8$), while the surface (0–1 cm) and subsurface layers remain relatively high, though with some interannual reduction and increased scatter in intermediate layers. Importantly, the boxplots indicate increased variance (patchiness) in the deepest section in 2007. A wider interquartile range and longer whiskers indicate spatial heterogeneity in diversity at depth for that year.

During the 2006 neutral ENSO phase, the 0–1 cm section exhibited the highest Chao2 estimate (31.67), suggesting approximately 4.67 undetected taxa beyond the 25 observed (14.7% undetected). These estimates declined progressively with increasing sediment depth. For example, whereas the 5–10 cm section showed near-complete sampling during La Niña (Chao2 = 17.33, observed = 17, only 1.9% undetected), the same depth stratum in 2006 suggested approximately 9% undetected richness. The ratio of observed to estimated richness varied considerably between years and depths, with sampling completeness ranging from 72% to 98%. Conversely, the 1–2 cm section exhibited substantially lower sampling completeness during La Niña (72.4%) compared to neutral conditions (92.1%).

3.2. Vertical Distribution of Density and Biomass

The total meiofaunal density (0–10 cm) fluctuated between 3916 ± 2202 Ind 10 cm⁻² in 2006 (Neutral) and 4203 ± 2274 Ind 10 cm⁻² in 2007 (moderate La Niña) (Table 1), and although meiofauna showed a slight increase from 2006 to 2007, this was non-significant ($U = 3.5$, $p = 0.20$).

With respect to vertical distribution, in 2006, the sediment section with the highest density was 0–1 cm (1506 ± 719 Ind 10 cm⁻²), values explained mainly by the high

abundance of *Desmodora* sp. (688 ± 369 Ind 10 cm^{-2}). There was a decrease in total values in the 1–2 cm section (935 ± 946 Ind 10 cm^{-2}), although the dominance pattern was still led by *Desmodora* sp. (297 ± 318 Ind 10 cm^{-2}) and nematodes of the family Comesomatidae (157 ± 168 Ind 10 cm^{-2}). The 2–5 cm (1121 ± 1148 Ind 10 cm^{-2}) and 5–10 cm (354 ± 353 Ind 10 cm^{-2}) sections were more irregular in terms of density trends. They only coincided in the dominance of the families Comesomatidae, Chromadoridae, and Desmodoridae.

In 2007, the highest density values were reached in the 1–2 cm section (1793 ± 1204 Ind 10 cm^{-2}), followed by the 0–1 cm section (1278 ± 743 Ind 10 cm^{-2}). The lower centimeters of the sediment column tended to show much lower values, 2–5 cm (780 ± 587 Ind 10 cm^{-2}) and 5–10 cm (352 ± 268 Ind 10 cm^{-2}). Overall, the vertical profile in 2007 indicated a marked concentration of meiofaunal density in the upper 2 cm of the sediment, with a pronounced and consistent decline in deeper layers.

Regarding biomass ($\mu\text{gC } 10\text{ cm}^{-2}$), in 2006, values ranged from 80 ± 24 in the 5–10 cm section to 455 ± 134 in the 2–5 cm section. The uppermost 0–1 cm layer showed 238 ± 155 , while the 1–2 cm section reached 302 ± 69 . In 2007, biomass was consistently higher in the surface layers, with maximum values in the 1–2 cm section (500 ± 534), followed by the 0–1 cm section (376 ± 34). In contrast, the deeper layers displayed much lower biomass, with 262 ± 197 in the 2–5 cm section and 107 ± 95 in the 5–10 cm section. However, similar to the other metrics, biomass was not significantly different between the years ($U = 3.5$, $p = 0.20$).

The proportion of nematodes (% N) was consistently high (overall $> 85\%$ in density; $> 70\%$ in biomass) in all layers and both years, with minor interannual differences. At the surface (0–1 cm), % N was slightly lower in 2007 ($86.4 \pm 11.5\%$) compared to 2006 ($91.7 \pm 5.1\%$). At 1–2 cm, however, % N increased from $79.5 \pm 19.4\%$ in 2006 to $96.7 \pm 1.8\%$ in 2007. At 2–5 cm, values were comparable between years ($90.5 \pm 7.8\%$ vs. $90.5 \pm 7.3\%$). In the deepest layer (5–10 cm), % N declined slightly from $91.8 \pm 7.5\%$ in 2006 to $88.8 \pm 6.4\%$ in 2007. In terms of biomass, % N exhibited its lowest value at surface (0–1 cm) during 2006, with consistent values higher than 90% in the other layers; whereas in 2007, this biomass pattern was even clearer, with higher values in surface ($94.7 \pm 15.2\%$) and consistent values along the entire sediment column (Table 1).

The vertical structure of the meiofaunal assemblage was strongly stratified and consistent across the two sampling periods, with the uppermost two centimeters of sediment often concentrating both numerical abundance (Figure 2A,B) and most taxonomic groups (Figure 2C,D), and with a marked impoverishment of diversity and evenness in the deepest layers (5–10 cm). Taxonomic composition and relative contributions to total density corroborate this vertical segregation. The stacked relative-abundance plots (Figure 2C) show that Copepoda and benthic Ciliophora were recurrent at 0–1 cm in both campaigns and accounted for the principal non-nematode fraction of surface meiofauna, whereas taxa such as bivalve larvae, polychaete larvae, and small metazoans (rotifers, gastrotrichs, nemertean) appeared episodically and were almost entirely restricted to surface sediments. At the family and genus scale (Figure 2D), free-living nematodes such as *Desmodora* and members of Comesomatidae and Chromadoridae comprised the bulk of nematode abundances in the upper layers; deeper layers (2–5 and 5–10 cm) displayed a more reduced suite of dominant nematode taxa (Comesomatidae, Chromadoridae, and Desmodoridae), consistent with the loss of rarer taxa and a shift toward assemblages numerically dominated by a few tolerant or subsurface-adapted nematode lineages.

Measures of univariate diversity and evenness align with these compositional patterns. Both Shannon's H' (\log_2) and Simpson's $1 - \lambda$ reached their highest median values in surface (0–1 and 1–2 cm) (Figure 3A,B) and declined progressively with depth; the deepest

layer (5–10 cm) consistently showed the lowest H' and $1 - \lambda$, and the greatest inter-sample variance, particularly in 2007. This indicates not only a reduction in taxon richness but also an increasing dominance of a few taxa with depth. The relative constancy of total taxon richness across years (no significant difference in S between 2006 and 2007), together with the observed declines in H' and $1 - \lambda$ at depth, suggests that changes in evenness (i.e., stronger dominance by a subset of nematodes) are the principal driver of reduced diversity in subsurface sediments rather than wholesale loss of taxa.

Figure 3. Spatial variability in the sediment column of the following diversity indices: Simpson's $1 - \lambda$ (A), Shannon's $H' (\log_2)$ (B), with a dendrogram (C) based on Bray–Curtis similarity of fourth-root transformed meiofaunal abundances, showing similarity relationships among sediment sections under Neutral (2006) and moderate La Niña (2007) conditions. Gray bars indicate significant clusters.

Multivariate structure reinforced the primacy of vertical stratification over interannual ENSO-related variation (Figure 3C). Hierarchical clustering based on fourth-root trans-

formed Bray–Curtis similarities produced depth-ordered clusters with high within-depth similarity (>80–90% similarity for many sections) such that surface samples (both years) grouped and were segregated from deeper-section clusters. Cluster analysis revealed significant groupings (6) among samples (Global SIMPROF test: $\Pi = 5.957$, $p = 0.001$). The test confirmed the presence of non-random structure in species composition, indicating distinct assemblages within the study area; however, with relatively diffuse group separations in some cases. SIMPROF-defined clusters corresponded to gradients in depth and likely sediment characteristics, reflecting spatial heterogeneity in community organization.

Discriminant taxa such as Bivalvia accounted for 17.5–20.3% of the differences observed among sediment sections. Notably, Ciliophora, Copepoda, and Oligochaeta emerged as key discriminant groups, contributing 14.53% (2006), 17.16% (2007), and 12.1% (2006 vs. 2007), respectively. In contrast, comparisons between study periods consistently highlighted the prevalence of free-living nematodes as the dominant component of the meiofauna. SIMPER analyses identified *Desmodora*, Comesomatidae, and Chromadoridae among the top contributors to within-depth similarity and to the dissimilarity observed between surface and subsurface assemblages, confirming that a relatively small set of taxa drives the vertical partitioning.

Canonical correspondence analysis (Figure 4) further illustrated a depth-related gradient of community composition. Surface samples plotted distinctly from deeper samples along the primary ordination axis and were associated with higher relative abundances of motile taxa (e.g., copepods, ciliates) and certain epibenthic/upper-surface nematode taxa, whereas deeper samples were associated with nematode taxa typically linked to subsurface or low-oxygen microhabitats. The plot shows a clear segregation of meiofaunal communities based on both sediment depth and ENSO period. The distinct clusters of points represent samples from different sediment sections, with the community composition changing progressively with increasing depth. Specifically, the pink circles representing the 0–1 cm section cluster tightly together in the upper left quadrant, characterized by taxa like Actiniaria (Act), Hydrozoa (Hidr), and Polychaeta (Poly). In contrast, the purple circles (5–10 cm section) are largely restricted to the upper and far right portion of the plot, associated with species such as Monhysteridae (Monh) and infrequent Tardigrada (Tard). The samples from intermediate depths (1–2 cm and 2–5 cm), represented by green and light turquoise circles, respectively, occupy the central region of the plot, indicating a transitional community composition.

Collectively, both the CCA and multivariate evidence indicate that vertical habitat heterogeneity, likely mediated by gradients in food availability, oxygenation, redox conditions, and by the differential life-history. The surface sediment seemed to support a richer community (including substantial non-nematode fractions), while deeper layers were characterized by lower diversity and by numerical dominance of a reduced set of nematode taxa, suggesting depth-related differences in composition.

In Figure 4, the red vectors represent the influence of specific environmental variables, while the vector labeled “ensoNeutral” points towards the right side of the plot, indicating communities observed during the Neutral period (triangles) are primarily associated with a different suite of taxa and environmental conditions than those from the moderate LN period (circles). The vector labeled “section 2–5” also points towards the right, suggesting that the community composition found in this specific depth range is a significant driver of the observed patterns along CCA1.

Figure 4. Canonical Correspondence Analysis of Meiofauna Community Structure. Acti: Actiniaria, Dich: Dichromadora, Poly: Polychaeta, Gast: Gastrotricha, Monh: Monhysteridae, Tard: Tardigrada, Oxys: Oxystominidae, Demo: Desmodora, Biva: Bivalvia, Spir: Spirinia, Lept: Leptonemella, Psel: Pselionema, Hidr: Hidrozoa, Cili: Ciliophora, Chro: Chromadoridae, Olig: Oligochaeta.

Finally, PERMANOVA results (Table 2) indicated that vertical stratification in sediment layers was the main factor structuring meiofaunal density ($R^2 = 0.0197$, $p = 0.005$). In contrast, temporal differences between sampling periods (ENSO conditions) alone were not significant ($R^2 = 0.0009$, $p = 0.462$). However, the interaction between ENSO and sediment sections was marginally significant ($R^2 = 0.0121$, $p = 0.048$), suggesting subtle year-specific adjustments in vertical community distribution. On the other hand, residuals accounted for 96.73% of the variation, indicating that most of the variability in density was not explained by ENSO phase, sediment section, or their interaction, suggesting that other unmeasured factors may underlie this unexplained variation.

Table 2. Results of PERMANOVA testing the effects of ENSO phase (Neutral 2006, moderate La Niña 2007), sediment section (0–1, 1–2, 2–5, 5–10 cm), and their interaction on meiofaunal community structure. Significance codes: ** $p < 0.001$, * $p < 0.01$, $p < 0.05$. Number of permutations: 999.

Term	Df	SS	R^2	F	$p (>F)$
ENSO phase	1	6651	0.00093	0.6046	0.462
Sediment section	3	141,242	0.01965	4.2794	0.005 **
ENSO phase \times Sediment section	3	87,121	0.01212	2.6396	0.048 *
Residual	632	6,953,034	0.96730		
Total	639	7,188,048	1.00000		

3.3. Production and Estimates Derived

The total production of meiofauna ranged from $2.836 \pm 0.049 \text{ gC m}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$ in 2006 to $3.106 \pm 1.566 \text{ gC m}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$ in 2007. Nematodes accounted for the bulk of this production, contributing $2.738 \pm 0.075 \text{ gC m}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$ (96.5%) in 2006 and $2.872 \pm 3.321 \text{ gC m}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$ (92.5%) in 2007. Despite the relatively high variability observed in 2007, these findings clearly indicate a meiofaunal community metabolically dominated by nematodes, particularly large-sized forms, as suggested by consistently low P/B values across both years (Figure 5, Table 3).

Figure 5. Comparison (average \pm SD) between Production (P) of Total Meiofauna and Nematoda for the study periods.

When contrasted with nematodes, smaller taxa such as Gastrotricha, Halacaridae, Copepoda, and Rotifera showed proportionally higher productivity relative to their densities. Among these, ciliates were especially noteworthy, contributing substantially to meiofaunal production in surface sediments: 0.113 ± 0.067 gC m⁻² y⁻¹ (4% of total) in 2006 and 0.301 ± 0.465 gC m⁻² y⁻¹ (9.7% of total) in 2007. Similarly to nematodes, ciliates displayed comparatively low P/B values, highlighting the contribution of larger-bodied individuals.

Respiration patterns paralleled production results, with nematodes representing the dominant contributors, followed by ciliates, copepods, nemertean, and polychaete larvae. Community respiration totaled 6.532 ± 0.112 gC m⁻² y⁻¹ in 2006 and 7.147 ± 3.581 gC m⁻² y⁻¹ in 2007. Nematode respiration alone ranged from 6.309 ± 0.172 gC m⁻² y⁻¹ (96.6% of total, 2006) to 6.611 ± 3.321 gC m⁻² y⁻¹ (92.5% of total, 2007). Ciliates again ranked second in importance, with respiration estimates of 0.267 ± 0.158 gC m⁻² y⁻¹ (2006) and 0.703 ± 0.465 gC m⁻² y⁻¹ (2007).

Overall, meiofaunal carbon cycling (P + R) ranged from 9.368 ± 0.161 gC m⁻² y⁻¹ in 2006 to 10.253 ± 5.147 gC m⁻² y⁻¹ in 2007 (Table 3). These fluxes were overwhelmingly driven by nematodes, especially at surface and intermediate depths of the sediment column (e.g., 0–1 cm and 1–2 cm), where their abundance was highest. Nonetheless, other components, including temporary meiofauna (e.g., polychaetes), permanent taxa such as rotifers, and protozoans (notably ciliates), also played relevant roles in carbon acquisition and turnover in surface sediments. Patterns of P + R largely mirrored those described independently for production and respiration. Only nematodes showed slightly higher biomass, production, and respiration in 2007, though differences were not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). Other taxa exhibited irregular patterns.

Table 3. Biomass (B), Production (P), Productivity (P/B), and Respiration (R) for meiofaunal taxa.

	B (gC m ⁻²)	P (gC m ⁻² y ⁻¹)	P/B (y ⁻¹)	R (gC m ⁻² y ⁻¹)	P + R (gC m ⁻² y ⁻¹)
2006					
Bivalvia	0.002 ± 0.014	0.011 ± 0.004	5.466 ± 0.068	0.026 ± 0.009	0.037 ± 0.013
Ciliophora	0.024 ± 0.254	0.113 ± 0.067	4.882 ± 0.230	0.267 ± 0.158	0.380 ± 0.225
Copepoda	0.011 ± 0.069	0.057 ± 0.018	5.091 ± 0.091	0.135 ± 0.043	0.192 ± 0.061
Gastrotricha	0.000 ± 0.000	0.001 ± 0.000	5.959 ± 0.000	0.002 ± 0.000	0.003 ± 0.000
Halacaridae	0.001 ± 0.002	0.005 ± 0.000	5.600 ± 0.017	0.013 ± 0.001	0.018 ± 0.002
Nematoda	1.028 ± 0.277	2.738 ± 0.075	2.664 ± 0.022	6.309 ± 0.172	9.047 ± 0.247
Nemertea	0.005 ± 0.007	0.026 ± 0.002	5.285 ± 0.015	0.061 ± 0.004	0.086 ± 0.006
Oligochaeta	0.001 ± 0.018	0.008 ± 0.005	5.531 ± 0.115	0.020 ± 0.011	0.028 ± 0.016
Polychaeta	0.002 ± 0.002	0.009 ± 0.001	5.506 ± 0.012	0.021 ± 0.001	0.029 ± 0.002
Rotifera	0.002 ± 0.012	0.011 ± 0.003	5.459 ± 0.057	0.027 ± 0.008	0.038 ± 0.011
Total	1.076 ± 0.024	2.836 ± 0.049	2.636 ± 0.014	6.532 ± 0.112	9.368 ± 0.161
2007					
Bivalvia	0.003 ± 0.001	0.016 ± 0.009	5.386 ± 0.047	0.038 ± 0.009	0.054 ± 0.012
Ciliophora	0.070 ± 0.052	0.301 ± 0.465	4.434 ± 0.409	0.703 ± 0.465	1.004 ± 0.664
Copepoda	0.008 ± 0.000	0.042 ± 0.002	5.169 ± 0.005	0.099 ± 0.002	0.141 ± 0.003
Gastrotricha	0.001 ± 0.001	0.008 ± 0.009	5.524 ± 0.090	0.020 ± 0.009	0.028 ± 0.013
Halacaridae	0.004 ± 0.001	0.022 ± 0.008	5.314 ± 0.035	0.053 ± 0.008	0.076 ± 0.012
Nematoda	1.124 ± 0.716	2.872 ± 3.321	2.690 ± 0.422	6.611 ± 3.321	9.483 ± 4.773
Nemertea	0.011 ± 0.007	0.054 ± 0.084	5.123 ± 0.192	0.128 ± 0.084	0.182 ± 0.120
Polychaeta	0.008 ± 0.009	0.041 ± 0.100	5.241 ± 0.311	0.097 ± 0.100	0.138 ± 0.143
Rotifera	0.015 ± 0.009	0.074 ± 0.103	5.024 ± 0.190	0.176 ± 0.103	0.250 ± 0.147
Total	1.245 ± 0.793	3.106 ± 1.566	2.628 ± 0.416	7.147 ± 3.581	10.253 ± 5.147

4. Discussion

4.1. Meiofaunal Occurrence and Community Structure

In anoxic sediments, where organic carbon degradation is primarily mediated through sulfur metabolism, the occurrence of a rich meiofaunal community is generally unexpected, as hydrogen sulfide accumulation makes sediments virtually uninhabitable for most metazoans [50,51]. These environments are typically characterized by low diversity and high dominance of competitive groups (e.g., Foraminifera and Nematoda), which have developed mechanisms that allow them to persist under such chemically reduced conditions. These include symbiotic associations with sulfur-oxidizing bacteria [23,52], high tolerance to hypoxia and sulfide exposure, all potentially under anaerobic metabolic pathways [53]. In addition, the small body size and relatively low oxygen demands of meiofaunal organisms confer physiological advantages compared to macrofauna [27,54] and megafauna [23,55], enabling survival in micro-oxic niches within otherwise anoxic sediments. The coexistence of multiple taxa observed in this study thus likely reflects fine-scale habitat heterogeneity, local oxygen microgradients, and biological interactions that mitigate the toxicity of sulfide and sustain diverse meiofaunal assemblages even under sulfur-driven biogeochemical regimes. In Independencia Bay, nematodes likely prevail due to their high trophic flexibility, rapid reproductive cycles, and tolerance to hypoxia and sulfide exposure, which allow them to exploit variable organic resources and persist under such fluctuating conditions.

Although some studies suggest that only anaerobic organisms can thrive under such conditions [52] and even report extensive defaunation [56,57], the present study revealed a broader taxonomic spectrum. Several groups, including Rotifera, Bivalvia, Oligochaeta,

Gastrotricha, Nemertea, Copepoda, Halacaridae, and even occasional Tardigrada, were found coexisting within different sediment layers during both study periods, resulting in relatively high diversity indices. The scarcity of previous research on meiofaunal composition in this region limits direct comparisons [39,58,59], especially for metazoan meiofauna. Nevertheless, earlier studies in shallow areas off Pisco have highlighted the importance of protozoan meiofauna [29], while observations further south (Marcona, $\sim 15^\circ$ S) reported comparatively high protozoan densities and diversity [30]. However, such densities remain lower than those observed in central Peruvian shelf habitats [60].

In contrast, nematodes in the present study exhibited consistently high densities throughout the entire 10 cm sediment profile, in line with previous observations from OMZ-impacted sediments in central Peru [16–18]. This taxon clearly dominates meiofaunal activity, reinforcing the notion of nematodes as highly adaptive, competitive organisms whose success should be further explored through genus- and species-level resolution. Specific species-level studies have shown that nematode contributions to ecosystem functioning are disproportionately high due to their competitive strategies and broad adaptive capacity [61–63]. For its part, ciliates also played a remarkable role in this study. Their abundance is not surprising, since many species establish epibiotic relationships with marine nematodes, halacarids, and copepods [64–66]. This strategy enhances their persistence in organically enriched environments. Moreover, the unconstrained vertical distribution of ciliates suggests the coexistence of both aerobic and anaerobic species, consistent with earlier reports on their tolerance to sulfide-rich sediments [67,68]. Such adaptations highlight the functional versatility of protozoan meiofauna in oxygen-depleted habitats.

Temporary meiofauna, such as polychaete juveniles, were also present, reflecting the regular input of macrofaunal larvae into the sediment [10,55,69]. Alongside nemertean, copepods, gastrotrichs, and rotifers, they contributed to a taxonomic assemblage comparable to those described in central Peru [18] and central Chile [70,71], both OMZ-affected regions of the Southeastern Pacific. Reports from nearby habitats such as salt marshes [72] and sandy bottoms [17,73] similarly confirm the persistence of diverse meiofaunal assemblages under oxygen-depleted conditions. The presence of juvenile deposit-feeding polychaetes, gastrotrichs, and a considerable number of ciliates, whose feeding strategy is broadly omnivorous, suggests that several of these opportunistic groups take advantage of periods of high organic loading on the seafloor to coexist with dominant nematodes. They do so both in the surface sediment layer, where they benefit from pulses of available food and localized ventilation, and in subsurface layers, where they are likely associated with the availability of organic detritus as reported for other regions and environments [70,74].

In terms of biomass, comparisons are scarce in the Southeastern Pacific. Estimates from Concepción bay, central Chile, ranged from 0.14 gC m^{-2} (outer shelf, 120 m) to 2.04 gC m^{-2} (inner bay, 35 m; [71]). These values partially overlap with those reported in Independencia bay ($1.076 \pm 0.024 \text{ gC m}^{-2}$ to $1.245 \pm 0.793 \text{ gC m}^{-2}$). While sampling here coincided with a Neutral phase (2006) and a moderate LN (2007), Chilean observations were made during the strong 1997/98 EN, which exerted a positive effect on local benthic biomass [70,71]. Given the limited sample size in this study, robust conclusions regarding ENSO effects remain elusive.

Comparisons with macrofaunal biomass across depth gradients in southern Peru further contextualize the results. Earlier work demonstrated that benthic biomass decreases with depth, but remains strongly coupled with surface productivity [19]. Although meiofauna numerically outnumber macrofauna [12,75], biomass values for larger metazoans are often higher [54,75]. Still, estimates from Independencia bay suggest that meiofauna contribute substantially to carbon cycling in OMZ-impacted sediments, with biomass values comparable to macrofaunal reports at similar depths. This aligns with evidence

that megafauna and macrofauna are scarce in oxygen-depleted Peruvian bottoms [7,76,77], pointing to meiofauna as the dominant benthic component in terms of biomass.

Vertical biomass distribution in Independencia bay was largely concentrated between 1 and 5 cm depth, mainly due to nematodes. This accumulation likely reflects the presence of organic matter in those layers [18,70]. However, the precise relationship between meiofaunal biomass and the quality and quantity of organic resources remains poorly understood in this study region. Comparisons with rhodolith beds [78] and sandy sediments [79] illustrate the exceptional biomass levels reported here; these findings underscore the importance of Independencia bay sediments as hotspots of meiofaunal biomass and carbon cycling under OMZ influence.

4.2. Production and Metabolic Requirements of Meiofauna

Independencia bay represents a typical upwelling system characterized by high organic matter input and chronic bottom-water hypoxia to anoxia, a condition also observed off Callao (12° S), central Peru [4,21,38,80]. Such oxygen depletion acts as a strong environmental filter for benthic organisms, limiting the contribution of large, oxygen-demanding invertebrates to local carbon dynamics [38,81]. Instead, benthic carbon cycling is largely mediated by smaller, tolerant groups, with meiofauna playing a central role in sustaining benthic metabolism under these extreme conditions.

Production estimates obtained in this study highlight the dominant role of nematodes in driving meiofaunal metabolism. Comparisons with similar environments along the Chilean coast reinforce this pattern. Secondary production reported for Concepción bay at shallow depths (35 m) reached $32.19 \text{ gC m}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$ [71], a value strikingly similar to the $31.1 \text{ gC m}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$ estimated for Independencia bay in 2007 in this study. Two methodological differences should be noted: (i) sediment integration depth (0–15 cm in Concepción vs. 0–10 cm in Independencia), and (ii) the seasonal context of sampling. Nonetheless, both cases converge on the same ecological outcome, indicating that meiofaunal production is largely fueled by nematodes (in this study, specifically identifying to *Desmodora*, *Sabatieria*, *Comesomatidae*, among other nematode taxa), consistent with their wide size spectrum, elevated biomass, and capacity to exploit organic matter concentrated in the upper sediment layers [62].

Respiration estimates followed the same taxonomic skew, with nematodes accounting for the vast majority of meiofaunal oxygen consumption. Given the strong dependence of production–respiration relationships on biomass, the pervasive dominance of nematodes across all sediment layers suggests an efficient colonization strategy (e.g., external coatings or endosymbiosis to tolerate sulfide-rich sediments, quiescence under low-oxygen/anoxic conditions, high reproduction rates), enabling this group to persist even in anoxic microhabitats [82]. Comparable findings across the Peruvian margin confirm that nematodes can regulate benthic metabolism in severely reduced environments [19,38,83]. These results highlight the disproportionate ecological role of nematodes within the eukaryotic benthos. Indeed, in oxygen-deficient sediments, much of the biologically mediated carbon flux is channeled through this single taxonomic group. Although benthic secondary production remains poorly quantified in the Peruvian margin and across the Southeastern Pacific, the results from Independencia bay underscore the relevance of meiofauna as functional drivers of carbon recycling. The region's upwelling regime ensures a persistent delivery of organic matter to the seafloor, providing a continuous energy supply to benthic food webs. The ability of meiofauna, particularly nematodes, to process and redistribute this input under chronic oxygen stress has profound implications for trophic dynamics and carbon cycling in one of the largest naturally hypoxic coastal systems worldwide.

5. Conclusions

Although the data analyzed in this study were collected nearly two decades ago, they remain highly valuable for understanding meiofaunal dynamics in the Peruvian upwelling system. The lack of comparable long-term datasets in this region underscores the importance of these observations as a historical benchmark for assessing benthic community responses under contrasting ENSO conditions. Meiofaunal communities in this shallow, upwelling-influenced area are not only abundant but also resilient, maintaining stable, Nematoda-dominated composition and density despite potential short-term environmental fluctuations. While it remains unclear what other forcing factors modulate the community and its metabolism, this study provides the first quantitative assessment of key parameters potentially affecting meiofaunal functioning and offers essential baseline information for future ecological and biogeochemical research in southern Peru.

The consistent dominance of a few taxa highlights the capacity of meiofauna to adapt to low-oxygen environments while sustaining key functions within the benthic trophic web. Furthermore, the evidence presented here underscores the ecological significance of meiofauna in processing and partitioning organic matter, thereby contributing to benthic secondary production and energy transfer. These findings expand the limited knowledge on meiofaunal biomass and metabolic demands in this ocean region. By establishing the first reference values for meiofaunal production and respiration in southern Peru, this study sets a foundation for comparative analyses across latitudes, depth gradients, and oceanographic regimes, and provides critical input for evaluating ecosystem responses to climate variability and long-term environmental change.

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Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

El Niño—Southern Oscillation	ENSO
Oxygen Minimum Zone	OMZ
El Niño	EN
La Niña	LN
Instituto del Mar del Perú	IMARPE

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